

Implementation Of New Curriculum: The Dalema Of Rural School Teachers In South Africa

Philip Kwashi Atiso Ahiaku, Gamede Bongani Thulani, Azwidohwi Philip Kutame

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 05,2024</p> <p>Accepted: August 06,2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Curriculum, Implementation, Resources, Infrastructure, Facilities, Rural Schools, Educators.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13225903</p>	<p><i>This paper examined the implementation of new curriculum in Grade 12 public schools in South Africa. The South African educational system saw curriculum changes in 1996, 1998 and 2011. The changes were to enhance development of education to improve quality and equality of education in South Africa. However, the implementation was touted by some challenges. A mixed method approach of data collection was employed. Questionnaires were administered to 129 geography educators and another 5 educators were taken through interview in King Cetshawayo district in KwaZulu Natal. The findings suggest that rural schools failed to implement the curriculum effectively because of inadequate infrastructural development, inadequate facilities and resources. Most institutions do not have access to quality instructional materials, equipment and facilities. Considerable teaching and learning time is lost because educators stay over 100km away from their schools and had to travel using public transport. The paper recommends immediate provision of the infrastructure and resources for rural schools. The study concluded that physical environments and provision of facilities and resources contribute to improvement in learning and teaching and therefore measures put in place to provide and upgrade old facilities and other educational facilities. Accommodation must be provided for educators to enable them stay close to their schools.</i></p>

Introduction

The national curriculum is the blue print defining educational development in South Africa. The curriculum defines the social policies to be used to improve education in the country. Since education is the driving force for accelerated economic, social and human resources much emphasis has been placed on its success. The success of education can be measured by increase in knowledge, self awareness and improve opportunities for individual's progress. In accordance with the benefits of education, the new democratic government since 2000 initiated restructuring of the educational system by implementing new curriculum. The new curriculum was initiated and implemented to rig the educational system of inequalities based on sexism and racism. Several curricula were developed from curriculum 2005, national curriculum statement and curriculum assessment policy statement all to reinforce the educational system.

The implementations of these curricula have been ongoing for decades and the variations in the urban-rural educational system is still visible if not more visible than ever. The implementations have bias towards the urban/rural divide with less quality implementation in the rural areas than the urban centres. The urban bias is not only limited to South Africa but worldwide phenomenon (Blignaut, 2008). These variations is a systemic deficiencies rooted in the apartheid political system where broader and conscious attempts had been made to deprive and alienate the rural areas from interacting with the people, places, resources and institutions across the country. In this article we focus on the implementation of curriculum assessment policy statement in rural South Africa and perceptions of educators.

A number of factors affect rural services supply. The national and provincial governments have favoured the urban areas over the rural areas in terms of service delivery and rural areas are left with insufficient resources to support rural development. Rural jurisdictions are therefore faced with higher costs and cannot benefit from economies of scale that urban areas enjoy. The area may have more difficult time attracting and retaining skilled and professional educators (Ahiaku & Mncube, 2018; Ahiaku, Mncube & Olinaria, 2019). Most of these educators lack the professional acumen to support the implementation of the curriculum. Physical factors such as infrastructure, facilities and equipments, distance to educational centres, road and transportation networks and provision of water can impede implementation of the curriculum (Rogan & Grayson, 2003).

We seek to shed light on important questions related to implementation of curriculum changes in rural areas in South Africa: does the curriculum change and implementation affected the gap between the urban-rural formal education divide? How do educators perceive the curriculum change from the rural areas?

Literature review

The reviewed literature is in line with issues that affect curriculum implementation related to infrastructure needs of the school, equipment and materials, resources for teaching and learning and time utilization and how the factors bear on performance and trust in the educational system.

Infrastructure needs of schools

Blignaut (2009: p, 88) summarises that:

“If the contextual realities in which educators are working are added to the existing problems, it becomes clear why it is so difficult to bring about change”.

Teaching and learning is made easy when good infrastructure is available, therefore, curriculum implementation cannot be successful without the relevant infrastructure. The lack of school facilities, such as classrooms, libraries, resource centres, school halls, desks among others impede effective implementation of the new curriculum (MacGilchrist & Hopkins, 1998; Blignaut, 2008; 2009). In most underdeveloped countries, the education sector is unable to adequately fund schools and this affects provision of quality facilities and affects teaching and learning in such institutions (Kelly, 2006).

Infrastructure in government schools in Ghana has been described as inadequate. Those that are available are also reported to be in deplorable state and unsafe to use (Kelly, 2006). The situation according to Kelly (2006) is worse in the remote rural schools where shifts are run to take care of the deficits in infrastructure. In South African context, schools are classified as historically advantaged and disadvantaged schools. The historically-advantaged schools have magnificent buildings and well-designed educational programs in contrast to the broken and mud buildings scattered in the locations and informal settlements (Rogan & Grayson, 2003).

The deficit in infrastructure development in schools makes it impossible to implement curriculum change on the same scale. MacGilchrist and Hopkins (1998) suggest that implementation of new curriculum should consider strategies directed at different schools based on their infrastructure capacity. A blanket implementation of measures across schools regardless of their infrastructure needs may only benefit the advantaged schools. Jansen (1999) argues that a new curriculum like NCS and CAPS in South Africa must take cognisance of these measures in order not to disadvantage the already disadvantaged. He advocates a strategy that is deliberately directed positively towards the disadvantaged schools.

Lack of equipment and materials

The infrastructure needs of schools are closely linked with provision of facilities. Schools should have well-furnished classrooms with desks, tables and chairs, libraries stock with relevant books and computer centres ready for implementation of new curriculum. Kelly (2006) reports limited supply of instructional materials and equipment, such as science equipment, library and even writing materials, such as chalk in schools in Sub-Saharan Africa. He explained that the inadequacies and battered materials are to be shared by a large population of learners creating over-crowding which makes it impossible for effective learning and teaching to take place (Kelly, 2006). This kind of imbalanced situation will not promote effective implementation of a new curriculum.

Most schools in South Africa are battling with inadequate facilities and equipment. There are still schools without computer centres, libraries and laboratories and constant supply of electricity. National Educational Infrastructure Management System (NEIMS) report of 2019 indicates that there are over 5000 schools without laboratories, about 1500 are without computer centres and about 343 schools without electricity. This rather bleak situation poses a threat to teaching and learning of Geography since all these facilities make teaching and learning of the subject effective (NEIMS, 2019)

Availability of Resources

Resources form part of the essential tools for the implementation of curriculum reforms; one such resource is the textbook. Textbooks are valuable resource for the success of implementing the new curriculum (Tani, 2014). It is necessary, therefore, to prepare textbooks according to the new curriculum in order to achieve the defined pedagogy and learning strategies (Yasar & Seremet, 2009; Tani, 2014). As a guide to curriculum development and implementation, textbooks must contain what is required to be taught in the Geography classrooms and must be available at the start of the implementation of the change. In Finland, Geography textbooks are written and often treated synonymously as curriculum, hence, the textbook content is what is taught in the classroom (Tani, 2014).

One important characteristic of Geography textbook is that it must give enough space to discovery, exploratory and expository learning strategies (Yasar & Seremet, 2008). These learning strategies must capacitate and encourage learners to take part in research and increase learner motivation in the teaching-learning process (Yasar & Seremet, 2009). Yasar (2008) further states that Geography textbooks should be written clearly and concisely and take into consideration all cognitive levels; both low order and high order should be satisfied. Reinfried (2004) is of the view that Geography textbooks must be written clearly with illustrations and pictures since learners prefer pictures to enable them encounter the real world, however, there has been some concern

expressed about the standard and quality of high school Geography textbooks. Researchers have found that some textbooks do not meet the required standard and quality, because they do not have the required materials and are written with very scanty information (Wilmot & Irwin, 2015; Manik & Malahlela, 2018). In an analysis of six Geography textbooks, Ngubene (2009) identifies some shortcomings with regard to the content and assessments. His first assertion was that the textbooks contain only formal knowledge with limited everyday knowledge of the learners. The textbooks were found to have unbalanced assessment tasks, contrary to Yasar's (2008) view that Geography textbook should have balanced information on the different cognitive levels. Most of the questions in the text were on understanding, with few questions challenging learner cognitive levels of reasoning (Ngubene, 2009). Similar study in the Scandinavia schools identifies various degrees of anomalies in the Geography textbooks. Manik and Malahlela (2018) identify a mismatch between texts and illustrations especially in the human Geography textbooks.

Despite the shortcomings in the writings and material contents, it is worrisome to realise that schools do not receive textbooks before the start of the program. In South Africa, textbook distribution to schools has been a contentious issue (Blignaut, 2009; Mtshali, 2013; Manik & Malahlela, 2018). Textbook supply to schools in South Africa is constrained by funding. The issue of selection and availability of textbook must be addressed by the curriculum formulators. Failure to address these issues would cause educators to teach the old things from the previous curriculum instead of the new one (Mustafa, 2013).

The NCS and CAPS have embraced the inclusion of Information Communication Technology and it is receiving increasing attention (Department of Education (DoE), 2003). In Geography education in South Africa, there is an increasing focus on Geographic Information System (GIS). This current computer technology was introduced in the General Education and Training (GET) and Further Education and Training (FET) phases to improve teaching and learning of map work and the technology includes the use of hardware and software (DoE, 2003). The hardware includes equipment, such as computers, laptops, DVDs, scanners and whiteboards while the software includes operating systems and program (DoE, 2003). Van de Schee (2003) postulates that the use of technology in the classroom to teach opens learners to better understanding of Geography lessons, especially, difficult concepts. In Singapore, technology affords learners an opportunity to handle computer devices (Lim & Lee, 2004). The use of ICT was an opportunity for enquiry learning in Geography where learners were afforded the opportunity to analyse digital images of the earth features and other geographical phenomena (Lambert & Bladerstone, 2000; Bénéker, Palings & Krause, 2015)

Even though, studies have not proven a strong relationship between the usage of technology as method of teaching and learner performance in the final matriculation examination, it encourages learner participation in class (Ncube, 2018). The challenge faced by township and rural schools in the use of ICT and GIS has been attributed to number of factors. NEIMS (2016) suggests that as high as 67% schools are without computers while about 6% do not have electricity. This report clearly shows that a high number of schools cannot utilize ICT nor GIS.

Instructional materials and teaching learning

The educator's ability to teach to the current methods of instruction of the new curriculum depends on availability of instructional materials. Fisher (1998) confirms that instructional facilities such as charts, drawings, maps (topographical and orthographic photo), drawing instruments and computer technology are very vital for teaching and learning of Geography. If learners are to accomplish skill and abilities in Geography, resources are vital. The problem of teaching map work in schools is gradually becoming problematic for both teachers and learners. The teaching of geographic information systems most of the time is reduced to paper exercises instead of practical use of computers and accompanying software (Eikli, 2013; Fleischmann & van der Westhuizen, 2017).

Time utilisation and curriculum implementation

Curriculum implementation and teaching and learning are time-bound. Depleting of class time on other things rather than teaching is detrimental. Significantly, most of the time lost is due to educator and learner late coming, not going to class on time, not going to class at all, not maintaining learning activities during classes and leaving the schools during school hours for training, union meetings (NEEDU, 2013 as cited in NEEDU, 2014). Many educators, especially those in the rural areas face transportation and housing problem and do not get to school on time and cannot stay in school until schools close. According to Wilmot (2017) educator staying far from school contributes to about 10% teaching lost time, annually.

Time is very important in teaching of Geography, especially, tasks involving mapwork. In his research work on curriculum implementation in Turkey, Mustafa (2013) identified time as a constraint on teaching mapwork. Educators in Turkey find the time allocated to teaching Geography insufficient and failed most at times to complete their curriculum.

Empirical strategy and data

Assessing the data needed to answer the research questions, we decided to use educators in both rural and urban areas schools to provide better understanding on implementation of curriculum in the rural areas over the years. Our study relies on survey conducted among geography educators. We decided to use the geography educators

because the subject is widely taken in almost all schools in the district. Secondly, apart from the natural sciences geography makes use of lots of resources that need to be examined. The respondents were either located in the villages or town and that makes it to collect data on the time use and effects on curriculum implementation.

One hundred and twenty nine (129) out of one hundred and eighty (180) geography educators responded to a questionnaires. Respondents living about an average of 26km from the towns were interviewed. Five respondents were selected randomly and were interviewed on dynamics of accessing services in the town and their satisfaction and attitudes towards the department of basic education handling issues of curriculum implementation in rural schools. To facilitate interpretation of the quantitative results, we focus the discussion on tabular results from the questionnaires. We presented the interviewed data in a narrative discussion making sure the findings were realistic and accurate (Creswell, 2014).

Results and Discussion

This section looks at the infrastructure and support needs of schools for smooth implementation of the new curriculum. The section looked at the physical infrastructure such as school building and a Geography laboratory. Availability of teaching and learning materials such as relevant textbooks, electronic equipment and teaching and learning instruments were also investigated.

Physical infrastructure in the schools

Table 1: Availability of Geography teaching and learning centres

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	24	18.6
No	105	81.4
Total	129	100

From table 5.31 a large number of respondents 105 (81.4%) indicated that they have no Geography centres with teaching and learning material. Very few respondents, 24 (18.6%) noted that they have Geography centres from where they teach their learners. This result indicates that most schools do not have a place where geographical basic teaching aids, such as globes and wall charts are stored. A well-designed Geography teaching centre promotes learning development among learners. This is the assertion of E1:

“I have large Geography centre well equipped and capable of accommodating over fifty learners at a time. This gives as a lot of space as an educator to manoeuvre and attend to every learner”.

This finding suggests that in well-designed Geography centres, learners become free and focused and there is always an atmosphere to manoeuvre and promote orderliness, however, the absence of such infrastructure and facilities encourages overcrowding resulting in disorder and misbehavior in the classroom. E5 indicated that:

“My Geography lessons are held in a congested classroom where all learners cannot be attended to during practical lessons”.

The essence of developing a new curriculum is to translate it into the classroom to achieve effective teaching and learning. Therefore, curriculum implementation should be followed by provision of infrastructure facilities such as classrooms, libraries, resources, laboratories and desks. The availability of infrastructure promotes smooth implementation of curriculum (Blignaut, 2009). However, the finding shows that the vast majority of schools are without appropriate infrastructure especially classrooms and Geography centres. The unavailability of infrastructure in schools in the study area supports the earlier finds that school infrastructure in Sub-Sahara Africa is non-existent (Kelly, 2006; Rogan & Grayson, 2003; Blignaut, 2009). The findings suggest that infrastructure in South African has not seen any significant improvement and that only few former Model C schools have appropriate infrastructure (Rogan & Grayson, 2003). The implication of this find is that schools are not promoting effective teaching and learning since classrooms are congested.

Availability of relevant text books for teaching and learning

Table 2: Availability of relevant text books for teaching and learning

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	90	69.8
No	39	30.2
Total	129	100

Table 5.32 indicates that most respondents, 90 (69.8%) have the relevant text books in their schools to enhance teaching and learning. The remaining respondents, 39 (30.2%), stated that they do not have the relevant text books. The fact that 39 schools are without relevant textbooks is an indication that there are schools in South Africa without relevant textbooks and this affectsteaching and learning in those schools. It is rather worrisome that there are still schools without the relevant text books, although, this study reveals what other researchers have found in their studies with regard to text book supply immediately and after curriculum implementation to enhance teaching and learning. The findings of Manik & Malahlela (2018) and Mtshali (2013) revealed that most schools in South Africa have limited text books. Similar findings were discovered in Turkey (Mustafa, 2013)

where schools start implementation of a new Geography curriculum without relevant text books. Implementing new curriculum without relevant textbooks may disadvantaged teaching and learning since educators may be forced to teach with the old textbooks with old ideas (Mustafa, 2013).

Apart from the shortage of text books, most educators lamented about the poor quality content. In the interviews some educators stated that there is no single text book with complete curriculum content. E2 explained:

“You have to put a lot of books together to get scanty information for learners. It is worst when you give learners home work to do. They cannot write comprehensively because the text books have scanty information.”

The findings from the interview show that even the available textbooks do not have the relevant information to increase learners’ knowledge in and out of the classroom. This confirms the earlier assertion that most Geography textbooks in South Africa have inadequate information. Manik and Malahlela (2018) and Wilmot and Irwin (2016) and expressed their reservations about Geography text books in South Africa claiming that most textbooks do not meet the required standard and have very scanty information. This situation will not promote effective teaching and learning resulting in limited formal geographical knowledge offered to learners (Ngubane, 2009).

E4 also complained about lack of comprehensive assessment tasks in the text books during the interview session:

“I can’t get standard assessment task for my learners and I ended up giving them just very few tasks for class work and home work. I cannot be blamed even though I know it affects learners.”

Assessment is one way of consolidating learning among learners. This finding shows that the limited information delivered by the textbooks means that learners are also deprived of assessments at the end of the lesson. This finding was highlighted by Ngubane (2009) who found Geography textbooks in high schools in South Africa to lack assessment tasks and sometimes some mismatch of texts and illustrations. The effect of this is that learners have few tasks to practice in class and after school. The less the learners practice the less they acquired and are ill-prepared for their final examination.

Availability of instructional materials.

Table 3: Availability of computers for studying GIS

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	13	10.1
No	114	89.9
Total	129	100

From Table 5.33 very few schools, 13 (10.1%), have computers while the majority of the schools 114 (89.9%) do not have computers. This shows that more than half of the schools in the District do not have computers. It is not surprising that earlier reports suggest that more than half of schools in South Africa do not have computers (NEIMS, 2016). The absence of computers in most schools is an indication that teaching and learning of the newly-introduced GIS is hampered. GIS was introduced in the new curriculum to enhance teaching of mapwork by moving away from the traditional paper map to technological mapwork (Fleischmann & van der Westhuizen, 2017). Educators may not be able to teach GIS effectively without the computers and the needed software and learners may be learning GIS without hands-on activities. Learners may find such lessons very boring and uninspiring and may lose interest, resulting in poor performance.

Educators reacted to the absence of computers and software in their schools and how it impact on teaching and learning of GIS.

“The only computer we have is in the principal office and cannot be used because it is only one. I therefore, teach GIS as it is in the textbook”.E5 lamented.

“I remember some years back I used to take my learners to computer centre in town where they are assisted but these day I don’t do that because the schools doesn’t have fund for that” was a response from E4.

The result is an indication that a large number of our learners are not benefiting from the analysis of digital images and location of geographical phenomena using computers (Paling & Krause, 2015), although, the few schools with computers and software will benefit since the use of technology in Geography lessons opens learners to better understanding of Geography concepts (Van de Schee, 2003; Lim & Lee, 2004)

Availability of sufficient learning and teaching support materials

Table 4: Availability of sufficient topographical and orthographic photo

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
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Yes	78	60.5
No	51	39.5
Total	129	100

In Table 5.34, the respondents reported on the availability and sufficiency of maps in their schools. The majority, 78 (60.5%) of respondents, have sufficient topographical and orthographical maps. The remaining 51 (39.5%) indicate availability but perhaps not sufficiency. Maps are basic resources for teaching and learning in Geography; the fact that some schools do not have them is a cause for concern and this may impact negatively on teaching and learning. The voice of E3 on the issue:

“You won’t believe it is very difficult to get topographical and orthographical map. There are no charts, no wall maps and even common globes in the school.”

The result suggests that there are schools which are teaching Geography without much mapwork and therefore, not promoting the teaching of Geography effectively. This result is consistent with Fisher’s (1998) claims that instructional facilities such as charts, drawing instruments, topographical and orthographical are lacking in schools and are depriving effective teaching and learning. It follows that schools without these facilities are likely to have problem with teaching and learning and this will impact on learner performance.

Time utilization and curriculum implementation

Most respondents were found to be residing over 100km away from their schools. These educators travel by public transports to their various schools. This development is warranted because rural schools do not readily and descent accommodation for educators. Besides, most rural areas lack social amenities such as electricity and portable water. E2 explained the reasons for not residing in or near their schools:

“I couldn’t stay in the rural areas because of lack of social amenities. There is interrupted electricity supply and even what is worse is that cellular networks are not consistent. I therefore prefer to live in town and travel to school every day by public transport”.

The use of public transport by educators creates the condition for late arrivals and early departure from school. This result in considerable lost of teaching and learning time and prevents educators from finishing their annual teaching plans (Wilmot, 2017).

Conclusion

Even though the new curriculum provides the necessary opportunities for teaching geography, the implementation in the rural schools were with challenges. The reality is that preparations have not been put in place before the roll out of the curriculum. The curriculum change failed to address the issues of the infrastructure gap between the formal Modern C schools on hand and township and rural schools on the other. The lack of infrastructure in some townships and rural schools is an indication that the curriculum implementations were not successful in some of these schools. The absence of geography learning centres and basic resources such as computers, maps and charts in most schools limit the extend educators could teach and realise the implementation of the new curriculum. The lack of prescribed geography textbooks in schools hampered the effective teaching and learning. Most textbooks were without adequate content coverage and denied learners acquisition of relevant information. This is also a confirmation of inequality that exists between the formal modern C schools and the rural schools. The curriculum implementation reveals social inequalities in the educational system in South Africa. The schools attended by low income black children are deeply deprived. One expects that formulation and implementation of any new curricula in the country should take note of the inequalities and social injustice that existed and continues to exist should be taken care of. In so doing teaching and learning would be enhanced and young South Africans would be produced to meet the world of higher education and work, the black South African child living and attending schools in the rural and township areas are completely left out of good education and rather creating and deepening cycle of poverty. Quite a significant amount of teaching learning time is also lost preventing educators from completing their annual teaching plans.

Recommendations

The paper recommends immediate provision of the infrastructure and resources for rural schools. The study concluded that physical environments and provision of facilities and resources contribute to improvement in learning and teaching and therefore measures put in place to provide and upgrade old facilities and other educational facilities. Accommodation must be provided for educators to enable them stay close to their schools.

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Author Information

Philip Kwashi Atiso Ahiaku(PhD) (correspondent author)
University of Zululand, Faculty of Education,
Department of Social Sciences
Private Bag x100 Kwa Dlangezwa3886, Republic of
South Africa.

Gamede Bongani Thulani (PhD)
University of Zululand, Faculty of Education,
Department of Social Sciences
Private Bag x100 Kwa Dlangezwa3886, Republic of
South Africa.

Azwidohwi Philip Kutame (Prof)
University of Zululand, Faculty of Education,
Department of Social Sciences
Private Bag x100 Kwa Dlangezwa3886, Republic of
South Africa.
